

Supplementary Materials :

Connecting complex and simplified models of tipping elements: a nonlinear two-forcing emulator for the Atlantic meridional overturning circulation

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1. GIS Calibration

It is possible to apply the same calibration module, that relies on the independent forcing calibration experiments assumptions, on the GIS model Eq.(2),

$$\frac{dV}{dt} = (-V^3 + a_2V^2 + b_2V + c_2 + d_2T + e_{21}(1 - \Psi))\mu_V(V). \quad (a)$$

For the GIS, we must calibrate the coefficients a_2, b_2, c_2, d_2 , and e_{21} . In this case, the same operational assumptions described for the application of the calibration module to the AMOC are applicable. Specifically, two calibration experiments are required: one providing the evolution of the GIS volume over time under forcing exclusively by the temperature anomaly while keeping the AMOC intensity fixed, and another under the opposite condition, where the GIS volume evolves with forcing exclusively by the AMOC intensity. In this context, the coordinates of the bifurcation points are determined by,

$$\{V^+, T_V^+, \Psi_V^+, V^-, T_V^-, \Psi_V^-\}. \quad (b)$$

We denote *EXPC*, in the case of the GIS as the first calibration experiment of the GIS volume in relation to temperature, in which the forcing from the AMOC intensity is held constant at an arbitrary value $\Psi_V = \Psi_V^C$. In this case, Eq.(2) is written as,

$$\frac{dV}{dt} = (-V^3 + a_2V^2 + b_2V + c_2 + e_{21}(1 - \Psi^C) + d_2T)\mu_V(V). \quad (c)$$

This first sensitivity experiment provides us with the data for the following bifurcation points,

$$\{(V^+, T_V^+), (V^-, T_V^-)\}. \quad (d)$$

In this case with a single forcing variable, the method of Martinez-Monteiro et al.(47) yields,

$$a_2 = \frac{3(V^- + V^+)}{2}, \quad (e)$$

$$b_2 = -3V^-V^+, \quad (f)$$

$$c_2 + e_{21}(1 - \Psi^C) = \frac{T_V^+V^{-2}(V^- - 3V^+) - T_V^-V^{+2}(V^+ - 3V^-)}{2(T_V^- - T_V^+)}, \quad (g)$$

$$d_2 = -\frac{(V^+ - V^-)^3}{2(T_V^+ - T_V^-)}. \quad (h)$$

Finally, we refer to *EXPD* as the second sensitivity experiment in which we fix the global mean temperature $T_V = T_V^D$ at an arbitrary value but vary the intensity of the AMOC Ψ_V . This sensitivity

experiment provides us with the coordinates of the following bifurcation points,

$$\{(V^+, \Psi_V^+), (V^-, \Psi_V^-)\} \quad (i)$$

while equation Eq.(2) takes the following form:

$$\frac{dV}{dt} = (-V^3 + a_2V^2 + b_2V + c_2 + d_2T^D + e_{21}(1 - \Psi))\mu_V(V). \quad (j)$$

We cannot apply exactly the same calculation procedures for the coefficients due to the formulation of the AMOC forcing, which has a different form than those encountered before. We need to slightly adjust the calculation for the coefficients $c_2 + d_2T^D, e_{21}$ although the methodology to find them remains the same as above. Therefore, we obtain:

$$c_2 + d_2T^D = V^{+3} - a_2V^{+2} - b_2V^{\pm}e_{21}(1 - \Psi_V^+), \quad (k)$$

$$e_{21} = -\frac{(V^+ - V^-)^3}{2(\Psi_V^- - \Psi_V^+)}. \quad (l)$$

By combining the ATCM, which has demonstrated its validity, with this additional calibration section based on two complex model experiments of the GIS, we form the AMOC-GIS Tipping Cascade Calibration Module (AGTCCM). Further details can be found in the MSc Thesis by A. Laridon (52). This model uses the calibration technique based on the independent forcing hypothesis to better constrain the interactions between the AMOC and the GIS. This approach allows for the assessment, with the help of a conceptual yet calibrated model, of the joint evolution of the AMOC and GIS under realistic emission scenarios.

2. Parameterization of the AMOC with Three Forcing Variables

We present an example of a generalization of the ATCM in the case where a third forcing variable is added to the AMOC. Physically, it is interesting to separate the freshwater flux forcing into two components: F_{GIS} , associated with the melting of the GIS, and F_O , which is related to changes in the precipitation-evaporation ($P - E$) balance over the Atlantic basin. Indeed, it has been shown that, due to climate warming, these variations could have a significant impact on the collapse of the AMOC (21–23). In this context, Laridon (52) developed the following parameterization, labelled *ParamB*, for the AMOC model.

$$\frac{d\Psi}{dt} = (-\Psi^3 + a_1\Psi^2 + b_1\Psi + c_1 + d_1T + e_{12}F_{GIS}(V) + fF_O)\mu_\Psi(\Psi). \quad (m)$$

To apply the ATCM calibration module, an additional calibration experiment using a complex model is required. This experiment aims to perturb the AMOC by introducing a freshwater flux derived from the variability of the precipitation-evaporation ($P - E$) balance, while maintaining constant freshwater flux from GIS melting and a fixed temperature anomaly. In this example with the AMOC, the operational framework becomes more challenging to implement; however, we can still easily derive the values of the calibration parameters, including the new parameter f . One observes the inherent limitation of generalizing to more forcing variables in this calibration method, namely that the independent parameter c_1 will now be determined by three factors rather than two. This introduces a new source of error, and the trade-off in the value at which c_1 should be calibrated will involve balancing three dynamics, rather than just two. Further details, as well as the calculated values of the coefficients, can be found in Laridon (52) and in the notebook *SURFER_pre3.0_ATCM.ipynb*.

3. cGENIE Experiments

Supplementary Figure 1 | Temperature forcing in the calibration experiment *EXPA* and validation experiment *val_exp_1* with cGENIE. *EXPA*, consist of a 20,000-year simulation with a prescribed CO_2 forcing designed to generate a global atmospheric mean temperature anomaly. The forcing was parameterized as a linear function, increasing from 280 ppm to 2,800 ppm. Through the internal dynamics of cGENIE, this forcing translated into a global mean 2-meter surface air temperature anomaly, starting from $T = 0^\circ C$ and reaching $T = 10^\circ C$ after 20,000 years.

Supplementary Figure 2 | Hosing forcing in the calibration experiment *EXPB* and validation experiment *val_exp_1* with cGENIE. *EXPB* involved a 20,000 year hosing simulation with freshwater flux forcing ranging from 0 Sv to 0.2 Sv, which is sufficient to induce the collapse of the AMOC in cGENIE. The duration of *EXPB* was choose to ensure that the AMOC is forced sufficiently slowly, allowing it to remain in equilibrium and produce an hysteresis experiment.

Supplementary Figure 3 | Hosing region in the calibration experiment *EXPB* and validation experiment *val_exp_1* with cGENIE. The freshwater hosing was applied between 20°N and 50°N across the entire width of the Atlantic.

4. cGENIE Hysteresis for Calibrating the Second Tipping Point

Supplementary Figure 4 | Bifurcation diagrams of cGENIE and ATCM in the (T, F_{GIS}) forcing space from Laridon (52). The two hysteresis produced by cGENIE during the calibration experiments *EXPA* and *EXPB* are shown in their respective planes as solid black lines. The identification of the bifurcation points based on these hysteresis loops is marked in red, while the simplified hysteresis produced by the ATCM is shown in blue. The branch of the unstable equilibrium, which separates the two stable equilibria, is represented by the orange dashed line.

In Laridon (52), the calibration experiments *EXPA* and *EXPB* were significantly different from those presented here. The *EXPA* calibration for sensitivity to temperature anomaly involved a 40,000-year simulation with the same forcing variation profile as shown in Figure S1, except that after 20,000 years, the CO_2 concentration was reduced from 2800 ppm to 280 ppm over the following 20,000 years. For *EXPB*, it was also a 20,000-year run, but this time with a hosing experiment that began with a flux of -0.2 Sv in the region defined in Figure S3, gradually increasing to 0.3 Sv over 10,000 years. The flux was then reversed at the same rate during the remaining 10,000 years of the simulation.

Therefore, these calibration experiments were hysteresis experiments, which also simulated the recovery of the AMOC once the forcing variables returned to their pre-industrial values. This approach allowed for the identification of the critical coordinates of the second bifurcation point, which characterizes the transition between the collapse state and the nominal state of the AMOC. Based on these two simulations, the values of $T^- = 3^\circ C$ and $F_{GIS} = 0.037$ Sv were identified. However, modelling this second tipping point is much more complex and involves greater uncertainty than the first tipping point (29,40). Furthermore, the primary interest lies in better simulating potential AMOC collapse scenarios for the future. Additionally, to improve the calibration of the emulator on the collapse branch, it was shown in Laridon (52) that arbitrarily changing the coordinates of the second bifurcation point improves calibration. For this reason, in this study, we reuse the critical values of the second bifurcation point from these two experiments to focus on longer calibration runs that more effectively capture the AMOC collapse at the first bifurcation point, given that forcing can act more slowly in the calibration experiments described in the main text.